

Application online marketing for sales of various products with natural dyes for the community service program partnerships

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Abstract

Batik is an ancestral heritage of the Indonesian people whose existence is recognized by the international world. This article is one of the additional outcomes of a Community Service activity (PKM Dikti Grant), which is funded by the Ministry of Education and Culture, Research and Technology (Kemendikbud Research and Technology). This activity is an application of research results on the development of the use of natural vegetable dyes in the manufacture of various batik products. The results of the training are in the form of natural vegetable coloring products, paste and powder, various batik products, as well as website applications. Furthermore, the results of the training are applied in production and in marketing, which are carried out online through website-based e-commerce.

Keywords: Batik; Natural Vegetable Dyes; Online Marketing; Website; e-Commerce

1. Introduction

Batik is the ancestral heritage of the Indonesian people, with various motifs of colors and amazing patterns. Written batik is always made with a philosophy that is different from one another. International has even recognized this one ancestral heritage. Indonesian Batik has the opportunity to be competitive in the international market [1,2]. This batik clothing culture is flexible to follow the times. Millennials are now producing batik with motifs and trends that are quite different from the 1960s, but have not lost the identity of this batik as a cultural heritage. The reason batik is still used today is because of the beliefs or traditions that have been attached to it, so that this cultural heritage is well preserved [3]. Natural dyes for textiles and batik are still very few in use. One reason is the lack of availability of sellers of natural dyes, let alone ready-to-use ones [4]. In this training activity, partners are taught to produce natural vegetable dyes in the form of pastes and powders. The natural dyes obtained are applied in the process of hand-drawn batik, cibori, ecoprint and dabbling. Then in marketing using the online system. The batik conservation partners we trained in this activity thought that true identity of Indonesian batik was hand-drawn batik, but in its development, batik products in manufacturing process can be done in several ways, including punching, shibori, ecoprint and dabbling (Primary Data: Results of discussions from partners batik maker, Purwosari, Pasuruan Regency, July, 2022). Likewise, the design requires creativity from various aspects to create batik that embodies various meanings that have a sustainable impact [5]. This activity brought in 3 partners and dozens of people around the implementation location. The partners explained that they market their products directly through the stores they have set up. Through the results of explanations from partners who sell their products directly, while considering the effectiveness and efficiency of marketing in the millennial era. The Higher Education Community Service Program (Hiba PKM) Grant Team from ITN Malang made a breakthrough using the website to market products from various batiks that have been produced from partners.

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2. Material and methods

2.1. System Analysis

This article is the result of one of the outcomes of community service activities. The method used is to provide counseling, namely explaining relevant theories and applying them. There are 4 related engineering disciplines, namely chemical, textile chemistry, industrial and informatics. By applying the collaboration method, it is hoped that the results of community service can produce maximum output and can be used for partners. Based on a statement from partners that their products are marketed directly from shops. Evaluation refers to online marketing having higher selling power. The use of SWOT analysis to determine the capability of written batik products to compete in the online market. SWOT analysis tends to evaluate the strengths of a product when it is marketed online (strength), taking into account the product's weaknesses (weaknesses), then calculating the benefits that can be obtained by marketing various batik products online (opportunities), as well as considering the existing threats both from internal producers, competitors, and consumers (threats), [6]. To overcome competition with various products that are a necessity as well as fashion and to increase sales volume, it is recommended that business actors use celebrity as a means of promotion [7]

2.2. System Requirements Analysis

System requirements are divided into functional and non-functional requirements. Making this online link has a functional requirement in the form of features such as a homepage to delivery confirmation, while the non-functional requirement is in the form of various batik products that will be marketed through this website, [8,9]

2.3. Online Marketing Design System

Online marketing (Internet Marketing/E-Marketing) is considered more profitable [10,11]. So the steps for implementing an online marketing system for various batik products:

- Create a business process flow from upstream to downstream online marketing with the BPMN diagram
- Determine the entities and sub-entities involved in an online marketing business process.
- Creating graphical displays on a web to connect consumers with producers according to their needs.

2.4. Implementation

Online marketing is very much needed in the current era. Even though Covid has subsided, people are used to the habit of carrying out activities online which can indeed provide great benefits [12]. For online marketing, an open source framework is used so that partners can market their products through the links that have been designed [13]. This link is designed so that partners can directly upload the products that have been produced personally. This link is also equipped with a "batik category" feature to make it easier for consumers to choose products according to their interests

3. Results and discussion

This training generates a link that has a .com domain which in other words this website can be accessed by all internet users. Product sales from partners can go international. The following is result website menu

3.1. Home

The initial appearance when the link is opened, consumers will immediately arrive at the home page menu which contains category features, and some of the latest products from partners

Figure 1 Home page rumahapem.com website

3.2. Information

The information feature contains the profile filled out by the administrator of the rumahapem.com link, then the steps for making transactions via the rumahapem.com link, and tutorials on using various batik products according to current trends.

Figure 2 Information Display rumahapem.com Website

3.3. All Collection

A feature that functions to display all products marketed on the rumahapem.com link.

Figure 3 All Collections display on Rumahapem.com website

3.4. Product Purchasing Process

Beginning with selecting the product of interest, then click and entering the interface for determining the quantity of goods to be purchased, then immediately redirecting to the order data, then click "finished shopping" and immediately enter the user and password that was created and payment for the transaction will be made also through the VA app.

Figure 4 The Purchasing Process for Rumahapem.com Website

3.5. Tracking Order

Features for users to find out the status of products that have been ordered.

Figure 5 Tracking Order Display rumahapem.com website

3.6. Payment Confirmation

A feature that functions to find out whether payments from consumer users have been recorded in the link system.

Figure 6 Confirmation Display of Payment Rumahapem.com website

4. Conclusion

This e-commerce link that has been developed is very helpful for partners in marketing the various batik products that have been produced. The use of an open source domain server also makes it easier for consumers to determine the choice of batik products they are interested in. This link facilitates the transaction process between merchants and consumers, especially in today's digital era. It is hoped that by using the rumahapem.com website, which has been produced from the community service program by team National Institute of Technology Malang, East Java, Indonesia, batik partners can increase their sales as well as buyers can make purchases easily and quickly.

Compliance with ethical standard

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

This research is a collaboration of 4 Engineering disciplines, owned by the three authors of this article, namely Chemical, Textile Chemical, Industrial, and Informatics. In writing this article the emphasis is on capturing market opportunities through the use of websites. The study of the production of batik dyes and fabrics is discussed in other journal articles with first author Is Faidliyah Nilna Minah. The copyright output of the website first author is Ahmad Faisol.

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